

Nurses on the Frontline Against the COVID-19 Pandemic: An Experience

Rekha R Gupta

Dean, People's College of Nursing and Research Centre, People's University, Bhanpur, Bhopal

BACKGROUND:

Corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) was first reported from Wuhan, China in late December 2019 and was declared a global pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) on March 11, 2020. As on November 23, 2021, the COVID-19 pandemic has infected more than 256 million individuals globally, leading to 5 million deaths and has disrupted health care systems across the world.^[1] Nursing staff, who have always been key frontline health care workers, have been instrumental in the COVID-19 response worldwide, often at the cost of their own physical and emotional well-being^[2,3]

The first case of COVID – 19 was reported in India on January 27, 2020, in Kerala, and the first case was diagnosed on March 9, 2020 in MP Central India. In this article, an effort is taken to describe the experience of managing team of nurses who were at the forefront against COVID-19, ably supported by others such as patient navigators, clinical research staff, and administrators.

The selected hospital is one of the hospitals in central India from private sector. Early in the pandemic, the hospital was designated as a COVID-19 hospital for all patients. There is lack of data regarding the impact of the double burden of COVID-19 and shortage of nursing staff in the face of lockdown, other manpower shortage, and personal challenges.

The hospitals began preparations to deal with the pandemic in early March 2020. Several policies were implemented in the hospital to mitigate the risk to staff, patients, and caregivers to ensure effective hospital functioning. The initial preparations included creation of a core action group to review evidence, create and update standard operating procedures (SOPs), and oversee daily operations. Nursing staff

were an integral part of this action group and expanded their services beyond routine hours. The action group communicated via a What's App group, and key members of the action group met on a daily basis to review the unfolding situation. The following areas were recognized for urgent action:

1. Screening patients and staff to identify those likely to be infected;
2. Setting up of a fever clinic and facility for testing for COVID-19 and
3. Creation of isolation wards and stepping up the infection prevention control measures.

Subcommittees of the core action group were created to look into each of these aspects. A team of medical staff constantly updated the SOPs based on evolving evidence. Subsequently, when selected hospital became a COVID-19 vaccination center in March 2021, nursing staff took on the additional responsibility of managing the vaccination center.

Screening of Patients and Staff:

One of the measures adopted since March 2020 was screening of patients and accompanying persons at hospital entry points, and thermal screening for hospital staff.

The staff deputed from various departments of the hospital like nursing, paramedical, dental and medical and administration. The identified frontline personnel were rendered intensive training on administering a COVID-19 questionnaire and use of thermal screening to identify high-risk individuals, thus segregating the COVID-19 suspects from others. Those who were identified as high risk- having history of travel, symptoms, high body temperature-were referred to a dedicated "fever clinic" for further evaluation. Others who were screened negative at the entrance were directed to access regular hospital services.

Entry access into the hospital was limited to only one person accompanying the patient, extendable to two if the patient was on a wheelchair. The frontline staff were trained to safeguard themselves from the infection. This training included appropriate use of personal protective equipment (PPE), social

Corresponding Author:
Prof (Col) Rekha R Gupta

Dean,
People's College of Nursing Sciences
and Research Centre,
Bhanpur, Bhopal – 462037
Phone No.: 8130989184
E-mail: guptarekha66@gmail.com

distancing, and hand hygiene.

Setting up of a Fever Clinic and Facility for Testing for COVID-19:

A section of the main part of the hospital near the entrance was converted to a 'fever clinic' where screened individuals identified as high risk could be evaluated further. Facilities for collecting swabs for reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) testing, waiting areas for those awaiting the results of the swab, and separate entrance and exit pathways to avoid contacts between suspects and other staff and patients were also set up.

Nursing staff worked in the fever OPD for sample collection, educating the patients and relatives, training other staff and carried out audits. We recognized that hospital staffs, in addition to fulfilling their professional roles, were also concerned about their own safety and that of their families.

Nursing students, having strong professional bond with the selected community, were identified as key members to play the vital role in spreading the right knowledge related to COVID-19 to community and nearby catchment area. Therefore, the process of training nursing undergraduate students and hospital staff on various aspects of COVID-19 started with the objective of educating and guiding the community in that area for reporting to nearby available health facility under Ayushman Bharat.

A group of nursing staff underwent the initial training and then acted as trainers for the other individuals. These training modules were conducted in small batches and included generating awareness about the symptoms of COVID-19, and precautions to be followed by all (respiratory and hand hygiene). In addition, they were taught about infection control practices to be followed in the wards and critical care areas such as appropriate use of PPE, measures to be followed while caring for those with COVID-19, and management of waste disposal.

Periodic audits were performed to assess retention of information and need for retraining.

A separate facility near the hospital was identified as an isolation facility for those with asymptomatic or mild COVID-19, who did not have facilities for home isolation. Within the hospital's existing facilities, new areas were set up by reorganizing various inpatient and outpatient areas to create segregated space for COVID-19 care. An intensive care unit (ICU) facility was created for the patients who required ventilator support and close monitoring. A separate pathway for transport of patients with COVID-19 was identified, rooms for

donning and doffing of PPE were set up, and several trial runs were performed much before we had our first patient to ensure that we were well prepared to safely manage patients with COVID-19.

Tracing of Contacts Identifying high-risk contacts of infected individuals is important to minimize the extent of transmission. Nursing staff created a group which had individuals trained in SOPs of contact tracing. The group powerfully conducted interviews of all possible contacts to identify those at high risk. The quarantine facility was set up in the hospital itself, while later on, other premises such as hotels and hostels were used as quarantine facilities. Testing/Retesting of cases and contacts Nursing staff organized by databases of those in isolation and quarantine.

Changes in Working Pattern:

Several changes were adopted to the working pattern of Nursing staff to attend to huge demand and work load in the hospital. The staff with high risk (pregnant, multiple co morbidities, and immune suppressed) were given medical leave during the peak of the pandemic. The staff from medical and surgical areas were retrained in critical care skills and deployed in ICUs. The duration of the shift was increased to 12 hours from eight hours. Monetary benefits too adopted to pay to nurses as 'Covid Allowance'.

Due to shortage of nursing staff, nursing students and faculty from nursing college too were deployed in the hospital. Due to acute shortage of nursing staff, 'Buddy concept' could not be implemented where staff is deployed to 'non covid' area, where PPE not required, in shifts alternatively. The much required 'OFF' too could not be provided to nursing staff due to acute shortage.

This led to many adjustments and physiological problems among the nursing staff. They started vocalizing their problems and difficulties faced by them. Few refused to work straight away and many started remaining absent in allotted shift. This absenteeism was managed by deploying nursing students of final years (IV and III B Sc Nursing) after convincing their parents and assuring them that their ward will be protected and will be looked after well. A transport too was arranged to pick and drop them for night shift.

It was found that most of the nurses had the responsibility to look after their family viz few had ailing old parents (15 %), few had very small babies to look after (25%) and few had to cook (45%) as home aid also was not available due to lock down, few abstain themselves due to social stigma from neighbors and

family (10%), remaining 05% did not verbalize the reason for remaining absent. Most of the nurses who used PPE for prolonged periods reported various types of injuries.

Many a times it happened so that the nurses did not report in night shift (33%). Many a times the nursing staff on evening shift was requested to carry on with the night shift too (22%).

The role of the nursing team in dealing with the pandemic has been acknowledged by the hospital administration as one of the most essential aspects of the generally response. Nurses presented their observations and learning in hospital meetings, in National and International webinars, to allow others to benefit from their experience.

DISCUSSION:

The WHO estimates that 80,000 to 180,000 health care workers could have died with COVID-19 between January 2020 and May 2021.^[3]

Several of them are likely to have been nursing staff. Bandyopadhyay et al looked at COVID-19 infections and deaths among health care workers and found that among those infected, nurses constituted the largest proportion (38%).^[4] The impact of the pandemic on the mental health of nurses has also been well documented, with several studies reporting anxiety, depression, stress, burnout among nursing staff.^[5] A systematic review and meta-analysis looking at psychological distress among health care providers during COVID-19 in Asia establish that more than one-third of health care providers suffered from anxiety and depression, the likelihood being higher with female gender.^[6] Lack of human and physical resources and the number of colleagues infected with COVID-19 were the strongest predictors of stress, anxiety, and depression among nurses.^[7] India and found that 12 to 14% of them reported anxiety and depression among frontline nurses.^[8] Nurses have been at the receiving end of bullying and social stigma due to the perception that they are carriers of COVID-19. In a study among health care workers in India, Radhakrishnan et al found that 70% of nurses reported a stigmatizing experience during COVID-19, and that being a nurse and working in a clinical area were more likely to worsen this experience.^[9] Most of these reports are from the initial period of the pandemic where transmission was less understood and fear was high. After several months into the pandemic, and recognizing the vital role that health care workers have played, such problems and stigma do not exist anymore.

a stigmatizing experience during COVID-19, and that being a nurse and working in a clinical area were more likely to worsen this experience.^[9] Most of these reports are from the initial period of the pandemic where transmission was less understood and fear was high. After several months into the pandemic, and recognizing the vital role that health care workers have played, such problems and stigma do not exist anymore.

The use of PPE is associated with problems such as pressure, headaches, sweating, disturbances of vision, and difficulty in breathing. It has been estimated that three out of four individuals who use PPE are likely to have adverse events related to skin.^[10] Nurses, due to their long-duration shifts and fixed postings in COVID-19 wards, are more likely to experience such problems. Wearing PPE for longer than 4 hours has been identified as a significant factor for adverse events, and limiting the duration of PPE to less than 4 hours could be the solution.^[11] The training of nursing students during the pandemic has also been affected, during pandemic the classes were suspended completely and students were called for clinical duties in the hospital.

Nurses have always been a part of a multidisciplinary team and recognize the importance of teamwork through collaboration and good communication. During the pandemic, the nursing staff has taken teamwork to new heights and worked in close partnership with several other departments —patient navigation teams, administration, medical staff, clinical research staff, and many others.^[12,13]

CONCLUSION:

The WHO had designated the year 2020 as the 'year of the nurse and midwife', in the honor of the 200th birth anniversary of Florence Nightingale. It is appropriate that in this year, nurses have been the champions in the battle against COVID-19. However, in the course of this battle, nursing staff have faced several challenges which need to be addressed to ensure their continued well-being. Health Care administrations should recognize the critical role that nurses play in crisis situations and empower them while they deliver important aspects of the overall response.

REFERENCES:

- 1 WHO. COVID-19 dashboard. World Health Organization. Accessed November 23, 2021 at: <https://covid19.who.int/>
- 2 Varghese A, George G, Kondaguli SV, Naser AY, Khakha DC, Chatterji R. Decline in the mental health of nurses across the globe during COVID-19: a systematic review

- and meta-analysis. *J Glob Health*. 2021;11:05009.
- 3 Bandyopadhyay S, Baticulon RE, Kadhum M, et al. Infection and mortality of healthcare workers worldwide from COVID-19: a systematic review. *BMJ Glob Health*. 2020;5(12):e003097.
 - 4 WHO and partners call for action to better protect health and care workers from COVID-19. World Health Organization. Accessed February 3, 2022 at: <https://www.who.int/news/item/21-10-2021-who-and-partners-call-for-action-to-better-protect-health-and-careworkers-from-covid-19#:~:text=In%20a%20Joint%20Statement%20issued,among%20health%20and%20care%20workers>
 - 5 Barrett D, Heale R. COVID-19: reflections on its impact on nursing. *Evid Based Nurs* 2021;24(04):112–113.
 - 6 Chen SC, Lai YH, Tsay SL. Nursing perspectives on the impacts of COVID-19. *J Nurs Res* 2020;28(03):e85.
 - 7 Baraka AAE, Ramadan FH, Hassan EA. Predictors of critical care nurses' stress, anxiety, and depression in response to COVID-19 pandemic. *Nurs Crit Care* 2021 (e-pub ahead of print). Doi: 10.1111/nicc.12708.
 - 8 Sharma SK, Mudgal SK, Thakur K, Parihar A, Chundawat DS, Joshi J. Anxiety, depression and quality of life (QOL) related to COVID-19 among frontline health care professionals: a multicentric cross-sectional survey. *J Family Med Prim Care*. 2021;10(03): 1383–1389.
 - 9 Radhakrishnan RV, Jain M, Mohanty CR, et al. The perceived social stigma, self-esteem, and its determinants among the health care professionals working in India during COVID 19 pandemic. *Med J Armed Forces India*. 2021;77(Suppl 2):S450–S458.
 - 10 Montero-Vilchez T, Cuenca-Barrales C, Martinez-Lopez A, MolinaLeyva A, Arias-Santiago S. Skin adverse events related to personal protective equipment: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *J Eur Acad Dermatol Venereol*. 2021;35(10):1994–2006.
 - 11 Atay S, Cura ŞÜ. Problems encountered by nurses due to the use of personal protective equipment during the coronavirus pandemic: results of a survey. *Wound Manag Prev*. 2020;66(10):12–16.
 - 12 Mulyadi M, Tonapa SI, Luneto S, Lin WT, Lee BO. Prevalence of mental health problems and sleep disturbances in nursing students during the COVID-19 pandemic: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Nurse Educ Pract* 2021;57:103228.
 - 13 Singh HK, Joshi A, Malepati RN, et al. A survey of e-learning methods in nursing and medical education during COVID-19 pandemic in India. *Nurse Educ Today*. 2021;99:104796.A

Cite this article as: Gupta RR: Nurses on the Frontline Against the COVID-19 Pandemic: An Experience. *PJSR*. 2021;14(2):41-44.
Source of Support : Nil, Conflict of Interest: None declared.